

Assessing the risks of enhancing the current Europe’s ADA web map with ground movement classification data

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Abstract: The European Ground Motion Service is offering data on ground movement across Europe with millimetre precision. With the intention of helping in the interpretation of such a large volume of data, the CTTC has already created an online Active Deformation Areas (ADA) web map, which can be consulted freely. The CTTC is considering the possibility of enhancing the said web map by including the causes explaining why ADAs occur. This article presents the changes in the self-developed ADAtools to make possible such enhancement and analysis of the impacts on the current implementation of the web map as well as an early assessment of the risks that such changes would imply.

1 INTRODUCTION

The European Ground Motion Service (EGMS) (European Environment Agency, 2021b; Crosetto et al., 2020) has made available to the public the deformation measurements of practically all of Europe. Three levels of products are distributed, namely: (a) the basic one, which consists of line-of-sight (LOS) velocity maps referred to a local reference point for both ascending and descending orbits, (b) the calibrated one, which is obtained by correcting the data of the basic product using a model derived from data from the Global Navigation Satellite Service (GNSS) as a reference, and finally, (3) Ortho, which consists of the horizontal and vertical displacements calculated from the reference data.

This constitutes a real plethora of information that allows for continental-scale projects to be undertaken. However, the interpretation of these data as they are available is difficult and complex, and it is convenient to use tools that offer a higher level of abstraction and consequently facilitate their understanding. The ADAtools have been carrying out this type of task since 2018; the most notable tasks they are capable of performing are (a) identifying Active Deformation Areas (ADAs) (Barra et al., 2017; Navarro et al.,

2020) and (b) classifying said areas according to up to four different processes (subsidence, constructive settlement, sinkhole, and landslide).

Initially, the ADAtools were used to process areas of limited extension—that is, what could be classified as local or regional projects. Since the appearance of the EGMS data, it has been possible to address continental-level targets. One example is the calculation of ADAs for all of Europe with the data available between 2015 and 2020, the first delivery of the named EGMS baseline: the European ADA web map (Navarro et al., 2022; Navarro et al., 2023) (see Figure 1); another project, currently ongoing, is aimed at the generation of wide-area differential deformation maps (Shahbazi et al., 2023) indicating the gradient of the deformation field, also from EGMS basic products and again covering mostly all Europe—although, at the moment of writing this paper, only a small part of Spain has been published. These two projects have been materialized as web maps and WMS / WMF layers. Both web maps may be accessed at <https://groundmotionadas.com/>.

The EGMS is committed to update the information it delivers on a regular basis; this makes possible (and advisable) to update, as well, the European ADA web map, incorporating the new information available. Since this means that the ADAs for all Europe should have to be recomputed, this situation may be seen as an opportunity to reconsider what kind of ADA data the new version of the web map could in-

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Figure 1: The web map for the ADAs of all Europe (<https://groundmotionadas.com/>).

clude. The authors believe that the most relevant data to consider would be the reason why ADAs occur—that is, what kind of ground movement process is producing these.

The next sections will describe what challenges (in terms of risk) that such changes would imply, considering the tools to use or develop, the impact on the current data production workflow and hardware resources.

2 THE TOOLS

The workhorse to produce the ADAs and afterwards their classification is the ADAtools toolset (Barra et al., 2017; Navarro et al., 2020). The main tools involved in the process are ADAfinder and ADAclassifier.

ADAfinder takes care of identifying the ADAs. It takes the Measurement Points (MP) distributed by the EGMS as input, producing the polygons defining the said ADAs as well as some data characterizing them, such as their mean velocity, area, or an assessment of the quality of the finding—that is, how probable is that the area identified as active be active indeed. ADAfinder is a seasoned, reliable tool, used in many projects since 2018. Therefore, the authors consider that it may be used for this new project in its current state.

ADAclassifier starts where ADAfinder ends. It takes the ADAs produced by ADAfinder and runs a series of tests to determine, for each of these ADAs, what is the kind of ground movement process that most probably caused it. Up to four different processes were checked by the original version of this tool: subsidence, constructive settlement, sinkhole, and landslide. To do it, it implemented a single decision subtree for each of these processes. Figure 2 depicts the one used by the landslide classification process. These trees relied on several datasets and thresholds (denoted as “Th01”, “Th02” and “Th03”

Figure 2: Single decision tree for landslides in the old version of ADAclassifier.

in the said figure) provided as inputs by the user. The datasets include a digital terrain model, several kinds of inventories (for subsidences, constructive settlements, sinkholes, and landslides as well as a geologic map) and horizontal displacement data. Most of these inputs are optional, but their absence will make some of the checks unavailable.

Note that, unlike ADAfinder, the original version of ADAclassifier was not a seasoned tool. In fact, it had some limitations and problems that prevented the authors to use it “as is” in this project. The next section explains why.

3 IMPROVING ADACLASSIFIER

ADAclassifier, the tool of the ADAtools in charge of classifying the different phenomena of ground movements, suffered from a series of defects that advised to improve or replace it before undertaking any massive data processing campaign if the risk of generating incorrect data was to be avoided. The most important defects were the following:

- All tests relied on the consultation of inventories (such these for landslides or sinkholes). The performance observed when querying the inventories was far from satisfactory. The reason, a non-optimal implementation of the polygon intersection search algorithms. In fact, said performance was of order $n \times m$, where n and m represent, respectively, the number of polygons to be queried (ADAs) and the polygons available in the inventory. Since the implementation of the inventory software was the same for all inventories the performance problem affected all classification pro-

cesses. This meant that processing a single EGMS burst could take about 4 hours; this might be perfectly valid to process a small area, but considering that there are about 15,000 EGMS bursts, the time required to finish the processing of all data would take about 2,500 days working non-stop. This problem alone would make the project unfeasible.

- Decision trees were too simple, due to the early stage of development of the concept when ADA-classifier was first implemented. The *concurrence* of different factors that could influence the classification process was not considered. On the contrary and based on a relatively small number of data and thresholds, an attempt was always made to reach a conclusive decision regarding the type of ground movement process that was being verified. This can be seen in Figure 2, which shows the unique decision tree for the landslide detection process in the old version of ADAclassifier. Note that the trees for the rest of the processes were of similar simplicity.
- The data formats accepted for certain types of information were limited or not very widespread. For example, horizontal displacement data was accepted in the format generated by los2hv only (los2hv is another tool included in the ADATools that computes the separate horizontal and vertical components plus the total displacement of the ground displacement measured with Persistent Scatterer Interferometry (PSI) technologies along the satellite's line of sight); the digital terrain models could only be used in the ENVI native format.
- The uplift detection process was not implemented.

The defects mentioned have a clear impact on three important cornerstones: performance, reliability, and flexibility of the tool. To address these shortcomings, ADAclassifier has undergone a deep revision and improvement process. Obviously, the improvements were aimed at eliminating or mitigating the mentioned defects: the performance of searches in the inventories now work in logarithmic instead of quadratic times, so processing a burst takes, usually, just a few minutes; new formats have been added, such as the popular GeoTIFF for storing horizontal and/or vertical displacement data as well as for digital terrain models. Additionally, the uplift detection process has been incorporated.

The improvements in the performance of this tool seems to make possible the processing of all Europe. The tests carried out seem to point in this direction; however, the authors are not sure that this perfor-

mance will be maintained uniformly for all available bursts from the EGMS, since such performance depends on several factors; one of them, for instance, is the complexity of inventories—tests have shown that when these include polygons with a very high number of vertices (apparently, more than 10,000) the performance is degraded, due to the increased complexity of the intersection operations.

Besides performance, the most important change is the one related to the reliability of the results. The new version of ADAclassifier now incorporates *a set of decision subtrees, and not just one tree, for each of the ground movement processes it checks*; for instance, the test to decide whether an ADA is a landslide consists of four decision sub-trees instead of just one. In this way, a much larger set of factors that may have some impact when deciding whether an ADA corresponds to a certain process can be checked in a non-exclusive way. Each of these subtrees generates a score; the scores of each subtree are added, thus reaching a final, total score, that collects much more information than that provided by the old, original ADAclassifier trees. Based on the total score, a class is assigned to the ADA. The classes are “It is not X”, “It may be X”, “It should be X” and “It is X”, where “X” stands for the different kinds of ground movement processes.

Figure 3 depicts just one of the four decision subtrees used in the landslide classification process. There, “ThLa04” stands for some threshold input by the user and the numbers on the leaves stand for the points scored by each one. Conditions such as “Aspect in A” or “VLOS is consistent with aspect” summarize some checks that are explained in the application's user guide.

With these changes, the authors believe that the new ADAclassifier could be a suitable tool for mass data production. This, however, must be confirmed in the near future, processing more datasets to gather more performance data for this tool. Therefore, the authors perceive a risk here that should be addressed before taking any steps towards the implementation of this enhancement.

4 AUTOMATING THE MASS PRODUCTION PROCESS

The transition from processing a small number of datasets to handling information on a continental scale necessitates the identification and resolution of a novel set of challenges before embarking on production activities.

The first challenge is automation. It does not make

Figure 3: One of the four decision subtrees for landslides in the new ADAclassifier.

sense to dedicate human effort to executing the different applications that will integrate the production workflow, dataset by dataset. Therefore, it is convenient to have *meta-tools* that allow the required tools to be executed as many times as necessary, reducing human intervention to the minimum indispensable. There are already meta-tools to automate the execution of both ADAfinder and ADAclassifier. Consequently, there are no risks related to the automation of these two tools.

The second challenge is related to the organization of information. This includes an important factor such as the systematization of the file nomenclature; note, however, that this issue is present in all mass production systems. Without a normalized nomenclature, it is impossible to automate production. Fortunately, this problem is not such *in this case*, since the original EGMS data source itself has systematized the naming of data; if this nomenclature is adapted with standardized variants to denote the different types of by-products generated by the system, the problem is solved. For example, given some downloaded file whose name is “some_file”, the variants “some_file.ADA” or “some_file.ADA.CLASSIFIED” may be selected to represent such by-products. This convention was already adopted for the first version of the European ADA map; now, it should be extended to consider the by-products generated by the new ADAclassifier.

Figure 4: Spatial overlap of EGMS data. Source: (Navarro et al., 2023).

More serious is the problem of how input data has been organized: EGMS has processed the Sentinel-1 bursts that overlap to guarantee full coverage. As can be seen in Figure 4, there is an overlap between contiguous bursts. This causes the ADAfinder application to generate repeated (although not identical) ADAs covering the same area in those zones where such bursts overlap (Figure 5), which, in the specific case of this web map, is unacceptable. Therefore, it is necessary to carry out additional data cleaning tasks due to how the information has been organized at the source.

This problem was already detected when implementing the European ADA web map and had to be solved by implementing the `purge.overlaps` tool. The biggest problem with this tool is the need to load all the ADAs in Europe *simultaneously*, to eliminate the overlaps at once (Navarro et al., 2023). However, the servers where this process is carried out are, fortunately, capable of handling the load that this entails; nonetheless, it is worth to remark the problem here, since it must be highlighted how the organization of data may impact in how data must be processed or, worse, whether it is possible to process it due to capacity problems.

Considering these two issues in advance (file naming and ADA overlapping) and taking the appropriate measures the risk of a project failure due to data organization problems is, according to the author’s standpoint, eliminated. Not considering these factors could, conversely, lead to a high-risk project.

No other risks related to data organization aspects are foreseen at the moment of writing this paper.

5 FROM DATA TO THE WEB

Assuming that it is possible to generate the classification of all ADAs in Europe using the tools (and meta-

Figure 5: The need to remove overlaps. Source: (Navarro et al., 2023).

tools for automation) mentioned in the previous sections, there are still problems to be solved. This section explains how data formats are one of these problems.

The new version of the web map should display classified ADA data, which ought to be stored somewhere. The most common way to store data to be used by web-based applications is a relational database, as for example PostgreSQL. In fact, this is the solution adopted by the current web map.

However, ADAclassifier generates ESRI shapefiles, which cannot be inserted directly into a database. Therefore, it will be necessary to create a tool to convert these shapefiles into files containing SQL (Standard Query Language) statements. By mean of these files it will finally be possible to transfer the information to the database.

A tool like this already exists, ADA2PGIS, but it should be modified to handle the new data fields to consider—at least, the code representing the most probable ground movement process causing the ADA. This would not be so great a change, but it should not be forgotten. Furthermore, the tool should be able to automate the conversion process as much as possible, considering again the issues (time, human resources) related to the processing of 15,000 datasets. That was

already solved for the current version of the European web map, but the changes in the data production workflow and therefore in the set of by-products to deal with would imply that the tool should have to be reimplemented to handle such changes. The authors, however, believe that the development of the new version of ADA2PGIS would not be a challenge, in terms of risk.

It is not just the conversion tool, however, the only element that would suffer a change due to the new information considered. The structure of the database itself should be changed, in fact, by two reasons: the first one, the number of elements in the ADA's time series (new epochs, and thus, new MPs are included with each EGMS update), the second, the code stating the reason of the ground movement. The authors decided that, although mandatory, this change should not be considered as a risk, since it is present event in the case the ground movement code is not considered in future updates, for the database must be modified due to the increase in size of the time series when new updates from the EGMS are implemented in the web map. In short, the risk of modifying the structure of the database would be the same no matter the number of new fields to include.

6 THE WORKFLOW

Sections 2 to 5 delve into the project's ADAtools toolset, exploring both existing tools and those needing development. Additionally, these sections tackle the most important challenges that must be addressed and overcome. Here, a global picture is presented explaining how these tools should work together.

Figure 6 depicts how, starting with the deformation maps downloaded from EGMS, the information about ADAs is stored in the database.

In the figure, green blocks stand for automated processes, that is those able to process more than one burst at a time—ideally, all the bursts at once. Note that the process to purge the repeated ADAs lying in overlapped areas is run just once due to the constraints of the problem. On the other side, downloading the deformation maps from the EGMS is a manual process that must be repeated until all the necessary information has been retrieved. It is expected, however, that improvements on the EGMS Explorer (the interface to download EGMS data, (European Environment Agency, 2021a)) will make possible the automation of these downloads.

The first three steps in Figure 6 would be mandatory even if no enhancements to the web were made, since incorporating the latest data updates to it can-

Figure 6: The candidate workflow: from EGMS MPs to classified ADAs in a database.

not be done without them. The greatest risk related to the changes in the workflow is the potential, still unknown increase of processing time due to the classification of the ADAs using ADAclassifier (see section 3); at the moment of writing this paper, not enough tests had been performed to assess it with a comfortable level of confidence.

7 THE WEB MAP

Drawing on the past experience from the implementation of the currently published version of the web map, the authors foresee no significant challenges to enhance it to show the new data about ADAs. Basically, changes are related to the way relevant information would be shown.

The goal would be visually displaying as much key data as possible without overwhelming users. While ADA's velocity was the primary focus in the initial map (represented by colour-coded painted ADAs), now there would be two key elements: velocity (as in the current version) and ground movement processes (the new data). Ideally, both should be visually integrated to avoid confusion and unlock deeper insights.

The authors envision a solution using distinct colours for the perimeter and inner area of each ADA, as illustrated in Figure 7. This approach would leverage colour coding effectively: the perimeter colour would represent velocity, while the inner area would depict the ground movement process. This convention would serve to enhance clarity and avoiding information overload, potentially improving user comprehension; this convention could be reversed (exchanging the roles of perimeters and inner areas).

Figure 7: ADA colour codes for velocity (perimeter) and ground movement process (interior).

This double colour scheme could be easily implemented using the styles included in GeoServer (see section 8); therefore, no problems are foreseen in this regard. The authors are confident in the technical feasibility of this approach.

8 THE SERVER

To make the web map available to the public, one or more servers are needed, which should host the applications themselves (the web map) as well as the software stack necessary to implement the service. Likewise, the data must also reside on one of these servers.

The server used with the current version of the web map is not affected by performance issues (Navarro et al., 2022). Consequently, the authors are truly confident that it would be perfectly valid to host the new version. Nowadays, information about the amount of data to store in the database as well as the workload that the server must support is available. The inclusion of the new update from the EGMS and, eventually, that of the ground movement information, would imply a rather negligible increase of both space or performance requirements. Considering that server is working comfortably with the current workload, there is a wide margin of manoeuvre to increase the volume of data or performance requirements, so no problems nor risks are foreseen regarding this issue.

The software stack and operating system of the server would remain unchanged:

- PostgreSQL (The PostgreSQL Global Development Group, 2024) as the database manager, including PostGIS (PostGIS Project Steering Committee, 2024) to store, index, and query geospatial data. These will keep all the information relative

Figure 8: The architecture of the server.

to ADAs.

- GeoServer (OSGEO, 2024), for sharing spatial data. Used as a bridge between the database and the web map. Transforms raw database data into WMS / WMF layers.
- Apache HTTPD (The Apache Software Foundation, 2024b) and Tomcat (The Apache Software Foundation, 2024a) servers. These are technology enablers. They make possible (1) to run GeoServer and (2) to have a web server to host the web map itself.
- The web map application. Relies on GeoServer to retrieve ADA data and on public base maps such as OpenStreetMap (OpenStreetMap Foundation, 2024) to add a background cartography layer. This is the human interface.
- The operating system of the physical server hosting the previous software components is Ubuntu Linux server edition (Canonical Ltd., 2024).

This selection of technologies incorporates only free and open-source software components. This has an important economic impact on the implementation of the project, as there is no cost to use them. Consequently, the adoption of this software stack reduces the risk of the project. Figure 8 shows the relationships between all the components making the system.

9 CONCLUSIONS

With this paper the authors are trying to assess the risks related to the addition of a new feature in an already working web map. This enhancement has been discussed in the context of a necessary system update due to the emergence of new EGMS data.

Several aspects have been discussed, such as the required reliability and performance of the tools intervening in a mass production process, the need for automation, the unexpected problems that data organization may produce, the change in data formats or database structure or the need of a server to implement the said system. These subjects have been explored under the light of risk assessment, trying to identify the weakest link or links in the chain, so a decision might be taken based on solid (or more solid) evidence.

The experience developing and implementing the original European ADA web map has proven essential to assess the risks of almost all the points discussed—as, for instance, how difficult would be to adapt ADA2PGIS to convert from ESRI shapefiles to SQL or whether the selected server and software stack would be enough to implement the whole system.

The most difficult element to assess is the new version of the ADAclassifier tool. Its reliability has been thoroughly tested, so the problem is related only to performance. Although it is much faster than the original version, not enough tests have been yet carried out to be reasonably sure that a mass production campaign may be started. The authors have noticed that such performance might be influenced by the complexity of the polygons in the inventories, so more tests are mandatory before any further steps are taken.

On the other side, the intersection of ADAs and inventories are just a subset of the tests (subtrees, see section 3) that ADAclassifier carries out. In fact, inventories are optional inputs to ADAclassifier; when not present, the checks (subtrees) related to inventories are simply ignored. This, combined with the fact that, usually, inventories are not available, might make the ADAclassifier performance issue less important. It is still unknown which inventories (for each kind of ground movement process) will be available if it is decided to process all of Europe. This, together with the performance of ADAclassifier, is the second unknown to be solved.

In conclusion, the analysis presented herein allows the authors to affirm that the enhancement of the web map is possible from the technical standpoint; no risk is perceived on this side. On the contrary, there are serious doubts from the temporal standpoint: the lack of solid knowledge about the performance of

ADAclassifier as well and about the availability of the inventories, makes very difficult to assess how much time would be needed to complete the whole project, and whether such amount of time is affordable. Further work on this direction is therefore needed.

Note, however, that the current version of the ADAtools is reliable and performant enough as to be used in local / regional projects. It is available for free and may be obtained contacting any or the authors.

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